

PLANNING AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES PEARLS

**Marie Skłodowska - Curie Actions (MSCA)
Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE)
H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017 – 778039 - PEARLS**

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Abstract

The deliverable 5.2. is a Methodological course on social analysis and participatory methods for the business and CSO sectors. This course took place online on the 27th, 28th and 29th of March 2023. Researchers from ICSUL and the company Ethics for Growth shared knowledge on citizen engagement, a tool-kit for policy co-design and implementation and Future studies applied to community engagement.

24 members from 11 organisations of the PEARLS team registered for the course and between 7 and 11 participants attended each session. The presentations and video recordings of the sessions were made available to registered participants. This report gives an account of the organisation of the course and the contents of each session, including the presentations.

Index

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Organisation of the training course.....	4
3. Training course	7
3.1 Toolkit for policy co-design and implementation, 27 th March 2023.....	7
3.2 Citizen Engagement Training, 28 th March 2023.....	13
3.3 Citizen engagement in renewable energies and future studies, 29 th March 2023	30
4. Results	41
5. References	42
6. PEARLS Consortium	44

1. Introduction

WP5 Social Innovation and Public Engagement aims to reinforce the social dimension in renewable energy development. It aims to explore how resources from social research can be used to enhance the involvement of communities, to tap into local knowledge to create innovative solutions, to defuse potential causes for conflict around landscapes and cultural values.

WP5 is led by ICSUL (PT) and includes 11 other PEARLS partners: USE (ES), UPO (ES), CLANER (ES), Territoria (ES), ENERCOUTIM (PT), COOPERNICO (PT), AUTH (GR), GSH (GR) and Ben-Gurion University of the Negev (IL).

WP5 comprises three tasks:

- Task 1: Case studies of social innovation and entrepreneurship in the energy sector. This task consists of the identification of relevant cases of social innovation regarding renewable energy (novel more sustainable solutions to problems such as community opposition, landscape impacts and under developed RE generation potential) through document analysis and interviews with stakeholders. A common template was designed for data collection in order to derive comparable information and best practices jointly with WP2 to WP4. A scientific paper on case studies of social innovation and entrepreneurship in the energy sector is under evaluation in the journal *Energy Research and Social Sciences*.
- Task 2. Landscape and cultural analysis. This task consists of developing studies on landscape and cultural factors in potential locations for renewable energy. Researchers will gather information on local cultural valuations of landscape and heritage in order to assess and anticipate potential conflicts and resistance to renewable energy facilities and help devise alternative locations or mitigation measures (through visual tools and other planning devices in cross-cooperation with WP4).
- Task 3. Training in social analysis and participatory methods according to WP1 communication and dissemination strategy. This comprises the organisation of a methodological course on social analysis and participatory methods, aimed at researchers and technicians from business and civil society organisations (CSO), and a final integration seminar with all participants in the WP, which will take place at ICSUL.

This deliverable concerns Task 3. It is an account of the training course that was organised by ICSUL in March 2023. The report summarises the content of the three sessions of training course, including the slides that were presented, and provides a brief reflection on the results.

2. Organisation of the training course

Task 3 of WP 5 Social Innovation consisted of training in social analysis and participatory methods, in line with WP1's communication and dissemination strategy. This comprises the organisation of a methodological course on social analysis and participatory methods aimed at researchers and technicians from business and civil society organisations (D5.1) and a final integration seminar with all participants in the WP, which will take place at ICSUL (D 5.2).

Besides its role as leader of WP5, ICSUL has substantial experience in organising participatory events of a scientific nature and providing training on participatory methodologies to its students, including a dedicated post-graduate course on research methodologies. The training event would also involve partner Ethics 4 Growth, from Italy, due to their experience in this area. Table 2.1 contains the short biographies of the trainers.

Table 2.1. Biographies of trainers

João Mourato (ICSUL): Research Fellow. His research focuses on the dynamics of the evolution of Spatial Planning as a public policy in Portugal. In particular, he analyses learning processes and institutional adaptation logics in the face of a changing legal, regulatory and political framework. He has a degree in Architecture/Urban Management and a PhD in Town Planning from the University College London with a dissertation on the impact of the process of Europeanization in the preparation of the National Programme for Spatial Planning Policy. He was a research associate at the Centre for Territorial Strategies and Policies of the Centre for Geographical Studies. He has participated in several projects on the prospects for development and territorial cohesion of the European Union. He was a consultant of the Directorate General for Spatial Planning and Urban Development.

Roberto Falanga (ICSUL): Research Fellow. He obtained a PhD degree in Democracy in the 21st Century (Sociology) at the University of Coimbra in 2013. His research focuses on the analysis of processes of civic participation for decision making, with a focus on Southern Europe in transnational perspective. He was co-principal investigator of the European Commission funded project ROCK - Regeneration and Optimisation of Cultural heritage in creative and Knowledge cities (2017-2020). He is currently coordinating the ICSUL team of the project funded by the European Commission INCITE-DEM Inclusive Citizenship in a world in Transformation: Co-Designing for Democracy, as well as the project "Institutional Model of Policy Evaluation" in a partnership between ICSUL and Planapp - Competence Center for Planning, Policy and Prospective Public Administration.

Ana Delicado (ICSUL): Senior Research Fellow. She has a PhD in sociology (2006) and she works mainly in social studies of science. She has been doing research on energy issues and climate change since 2010, in national and internationally funded projects. She is currently coordinating the ICSUL team in the projects PEARLS and PilotSTRATEGY CO2 Geological Pilots in Strategic Territories. She was a national delegate to COST Action TU 1401 "Renewable Energy and Landscape Quality (RELY)." She teaches on participatory research methods and is particularly interested in public engagement with science.

Giuseppe Macca (ethics4growth): Entrepreneur, passionate about sustainability and CSR expert, I have always dreamed about impacting the world. During my studies in political sciences at LUISS (Rome) I realize that one possible way of achieving it is by changing the way we do business. Travel addict, before getting back to Sicily, I had experiences in Buenos Aires, Sao Paulo, Boston Durham (UK). In 2020 I have launched the social innovation studio ethics4growth (<https://ethics4growth.com/>) and now I am also teaching Ethics and CSR in the faculty of international marketing of the University of Manizales (Colombia). I'm attending a PhD in economics at the University of Enna "Kore", investigating the performance of the Bcorps and the alternative development economic models.

Figure 2.1 Training course programme

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PEARLS
EMPOWERING LANDSCAPES

Training on methodologies for public engagement
WP5 Social Innovation
27-29 March 2023

27th March, 15-17 CET, online
Participatory methodologies with stakeholders, João Mourato

28th March, 15-17 CET, online
Participatory methodologies: between institutional spaces and civic activation, Roberto Falanga

29th March, 15-17 CET, online
Citizen engagement and renewable energies, Ana Delicado and Giuseppe Macca

Link: <https://videoconf-colibri.zoom.us/j/97826967552>

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It was decided that the training would take place online, over the course of three consecutive afternoons at the end of March 2023. The option for an online format was justified by the objective of reaching the widest number of participants from the consortium organisations, academic and non-academic, and by the fact that no secondments were being carried out at ICSUL at the time. Figure 2.1 shows the programme of the training course.

The training course was advertised among the project partners in February 2023 and a registration form was created. 24 people registered and Table 2.2 details their home institutions. The link for the Zoom sessions was sent to registered participants the week before the course.

Table 2.2 Registered participants by organisation

Organisation	Number of participants
Consortis	1
Coopérnico	4
Ethics4growth	1
Geosystems Hellas SA	1
Habitech	1
Regional Government of Andalusia	1
Territoria SLU	1
University of Huelva	1
University of Seville	9
University of Trento	2

3. Training course

The training course comprised three two-hour sessions, in three consecutive dates (27-29 March 2023). Each session was designed to raise awareness of the theoretical framing underpinning participatory methodologies, the methods and techniques used in participatory endeavours and the ethical and procedural issues to be considered. Trainers provided concrete examples of participatory methodologies, encouraged discussion with participants and in one case developed a participatory exercise.

This section summarises the content of each session and includes the slides that were presented.

3.1 Toolkit for policy co-design and implementation, 27th March 2023

The first session of the training course was delivered by João Morato (ICSUL), assisted by PhD student Vera Ferreira. This session focused on a toolkit for policy co-design and implementation. It introduced methodologies such as forecast, scenarios and visioning backcasting, concentrating on the later, as a widely used tool in managing the transition towards sustainability.

This session included a participatory exercise, in which training participants were divided into two groups and asked to fill in two Miro boards, one concerning the Radar for Change (Figure 3.1.1) and the other the Radar for Action (Figure 3.1.2). Group A worked with the desired end “Renewable Energy Infrastructure is Landscape-friendly” and Group B with “Renewable Energy Transition includes Fair and Just Citizen Participation”.

Figure 3.1.1 Miro Boards: Radar for Change, group B

Figure 3.1.2 Miro Boards: Radar for Action, group B

3.1.1 Presentations slides

Looking Ahead

tool-kit for policy co-design and implementation

João Mourato | Vera Ferreira

PEARLS | WP5 Social Innovation | Methodologies for Public Engagement

27.03.2023

Setting the mood...

Gaston Berger (1957): *"the future is the raison d'être of the present"*, in the sense that our actions today are explained and justified by the images of the future we wish to achieve.

1980s: TINA, liberal democracy and *"end of history"*, capitalist hegemony, neoliberal, extractivist, productivist, growthist, ...weakening of alternative narratives... the capitalist absorption of critical discourses (Boltanski and Chiapello, 1999)

The *"iron cage"* of neoliberalism, Dardot and Laval, 2010, "It is easier to escape from a prison than to get out of a rationality"...

François Hartog (2014) - society's "regimes of historicity", the way we relate to the Past, Present, and Future. *"The present is therefore experienced as emancipation or enclosure, and the perspective of the future is no longer reassuring, since it is perceived not as a promise, but as a threat"*.

How to act?

Levin et al. (2012) argue that the way forward is to **rethink the idea of path-dependency**. Traditionally, this concept is used from a retrospective standpoint to expand on the negative impacts of policy and institutional performance and interpret limitations to policy delivery (Berkhout 2002; Mahoney 2000).

Levin et al. (2012) **look into path-dependency in a prospective way**. In other words, they advocate for "the generation of path-dependent policy interventions that can constrain our future collective selves" (Levin et al. 2012, 123). By this they mean that **today's policy interventions should trigger incremental transition trajectories toward desired future policy outcomes** that, ideally, would gather support and be reached over time.

Futures...

Source: OECD based on Dossier et al., 2018.

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What it is...
...and *is not!*

Forecasting

Project Most Likely Future

Scenarios

Explore Alternative Futures

Visioning Backcasting

Assess Feasibility of Desired Future

A method

- *Visioning* (1980s) and *Backcasting* (1970s) are inseparable concepts.
- *Backcasting* appears in the USA, Canada and Sweden (vis the energy crisis) anchoring itself in the field of sustainability after the Brundtland report "Our Common Future" in 1987.
- *Visioning* emerged in the 1980s and 1990s with the incorporation of systemic thinking and participatory engagement. Since then, *due to the growing role of participatory approaches*, different versions of *Visioning* have emerged.
- Today, *Visioning/Backcasting* is widely used in investment planning, public policies and action programs. It is particularly important in the body of research on managing the transition (towards sustainability)

So...

- Begin with the Desired End in view (*What do we want?*)
- Going Back to the Present (*What to do to achieve what we want?*)
- Equate Step by Step the route to the Desired End (*What plan and priorities to achieve what we want?*)

- So... Part A
- Begin with the **Desired End** in view (*What do we want?*)
 - **Group A**
 - *Renewable Energy Infrastructure is Landscape-friendly*
 - **Group B**
 - *Renewable Energy Transition includes Fair and Just Citizen Participation*

C. Radar for Change [what]

- Rewind:** What changes should have taken place to achieve the desired future? (For example, new knowledge, financial instruments, new technologies, new political or economic structure, changes in institutional, cultural, infrastructural routines).
- Evaluate Changes:** Evaluate each change according to feasibility and the degree of control you can have over the process of making that change happen.

D. Radar for Action [how]

- Roadmap:** Brainstorm actions that can lead to change.
- Evaluate actions:** try to evaluate each action according to the impact they will have on the system to trigger the desired change and the effort that will be required to carry it out.

So what are we going to do?

Set-up > Breakout Groups – Each group works on 1 Vision > 2 Radars.

Radar 4 Change - 40 mins

Reconvene Main Room > Breakout Groups

Radar 4 Action – 40 mins

Reconvene Main Room

Speaker – 1 per group to present... 5 min

Narratives – 3 Key Action Lines and 3 Priority Measures

Q&A...

3.2 Citizen Engagement Training, 28th March 2023

The second session of the training course was delivered by Roberto Falanga (ICS ULisboa) and addressed citizen engagement. The first part framed the issue of engagement against the backdrop of citizen participation in the production of scientific knowledge and the balance of power between experts and citizens. The second introduced participatory methods and listed different techniques that can be used, highlighting Action Research. The third part discussed theories of participation, Arnstein's ladder of participation and the definition of publics. The fourth part dealt with co-creation and co-production of knowledge. The fifth part discussed the effect of the pandemic on participation.

Finally, in the sixth part, a set of examples of participatory initiatives in the city of Lisbon were shown: the portal Lisboa Participa, participatory budgets, BipZip (a programme for underprivileged neighbourhoods in the city), the EU project ROCK and the citizen's council.

3.2.1 Presentations slides

The slide features a solid orange background. In the top right corner, there is a white box containing the text 'PLANNING AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES' and 'PEARLS EMPOWERING LANDSCAPES' with a logo of a sun and gears. Below this is the European Union flag. To the right of the flag, a text box states: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778039'. In the bottom right corner, the ICS logo (INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS) is displayed. The main title 'Citizen Engagement Training' is centered in white text. At the bottom left, the presenter's name and affiliation are listed.

Citizen Engagement Training

Roberto Falanga
Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon

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Outline

First part: Power and knowledge among science, state, and society

Second part: Participatory methods

Third Part: At the crossroads of participation

Fourth Part: The rise of co-creation and co-production

Fifth Part: A picture of participation in the uncertain time of the pandemic

Sixth Part: Examples

First Part

Power and knowledge

Timeline

A long debate about the production of scientific knowledge...

60s: **civil rights movements** raised critics against the authority of experts

60s and 70s: **science and technology** should engage citizens to understand complex problems

70s and 80s: **consumerism** extended the role of private market in public sector

80s and 90s: **place-based character** of research with variability across disciplines and institutional settings

00s: **post-politics** brought delegation of decision-making to technocratic experts and growing public disengagement

Global systemic risks

Ulrich Beck's thesis on **endemic risks**: a matter of rational calculation

Changing balance between **benefits and uncertainties**

How to **live democratically** with risks? How to **manage technologies** to solve problems? What is the **balance of power** among multiple sources of **knowledge**?

The **covid-19 pandemic** is a global systemic risk that exposes these questions with unprecedented magnitude

Experts and democracies

Democracies have increasingly **incorporated experts** to build consensus around complex problems

What are the best democratic mechanisms for keeping **experts accountable and responsible** to people and representatives?

How does democratic authority keep **experts autonomous**?

Power and knowledge

Context is populated by opposite forces of power and knowledge

Sociology of knowledge: every authoritative knowledge is socially constructed and subject to the interplay of powers

Foucault: power and knowledge are two sides of the same coin.

Each society has its regime of **truth** that shapes subjectivities and discourse, thus particular modes of governing

Experts

Who are the experts?

People who cultivate the habit of putting aside their own **interests and wishes** to examine the world

People in possession of **specialized knowledge** that is accepted by the wider society as legitimate

What do experts do?

Experts can clarify the grounds of **public debate** and improve political capacity to engage in democratic decision-making.

Experts can **diagnose** injustice and opportunities to **empower** the general public in discerning a problem

Critiques

Turner: the notion of expertise violates the idea of **democratic equality**. If expertise is contingent, experts produce situated rather than neutral knowledge.

Dewey and Lippmann: experts ultimately speak for their own **private interests** rather than for the public interest

Shapiro: experts always turn out to be on **somebody's side**

Holdo: **assumptions** about ideology, public interest, and the roles people are boundaries for experts too

Chilvers and Kearnes: **neoliberalism** can remove the public from the centres of power

Institutional and peripheral engagement?

Open questions

While participation may improve **accountable science and technology**, there are questions that remain open:

Does participation ensure a **democratic governance of science**?

Do people possess enough **specialized knowledge and material resources** to participate?

When should participation take place, at the **stage** of problem identification or solution?

Should participation be issue-specific or more broadly exercise influence?

Action Research

Action-research in social sciences opposes to “neo-positivist” approaches and stems from critiques to expert knowledge

AR should bring **unwelcome and uncomfortable news** to build new social and political conditions in societies and institutions.

AR should not be conducted to implement government policies without subjecting political presuppositions and frameworks of justification to critical examination.

AR has a **generative** function because it provides tools for reflection, self-reflection and change.

AR provokes change by inducing small “**disruptions**” that require self-consciousness of the researcher about his/her role in the context.

Action researchers should address important problems and become interpretive mediators between theoretical knowledge and competing practical judgments

Action Research and empowerment

Labonte: people’s empowerment builds on relationships tending towards equity in **access to resources**

Farr: AR does not hold an **intrinsic empowering nature**

The ideal of creating equal relationships can obscure an intricate web of power and social **inequality** (class, hierarchy, skills, language use, etc.)

Third Part

At the crossroads of participation

Preconditions: the black box theory

Science, state and society build an intricate web of relationships based on different degrees of power and knowledge.

Policymaking is aimed to improve the practice of democracy although, according to Lasswell (1951), there is the risk of technocratic procedures to confer scientific legitimization on decisions

Black box theories (Easton, 1965)

Since the 70s, the enlargement of **policy networks** aimed to exchange actors' resources and knowledge to achieve goals

Networks can vary in terms of **policy communities** and **issue networks** (Fawcett and Daugbjerg, 2012)

In the 80s, **implementation theories** opened to the possibility to engage the public with the government as customers, as citizens, and also as partners (Hill and Hupe, 2002)

Opening the public

Arnstein's (1969) ladder has inspired further investigation on participation as the process by which members of a society (those not holding office or administrative positions in government) share power with public officials in making substantive decisions and in taking actions related to the community (Roberts 2004)

Lay and/or expert knowledge?

Citizen participation in public policymaking engenders civic competence by building democratic skills, overcoming feelings of **powerlessness and alienation**, and contributing to the **legitimacy of the political system**

Yet, as **conflict** is intrinsic to decision making, the higher the number of participants the higher the number of positions, interests, and points of view

According to Fiorino (1990), participatory practices need to overcome the idea that **experts** are more rational and sophisticated:

- Direct participation of amateurs in decisions
- Enabling citizens to share in collective decision making
- Providing structure for face-to-face discussion over some period of time
- Equality with administrative officials and technical experts

Fourth Part

Co-creation and co-production

Co-creation

Co-creation emerged in the private sector to maximise service satisfaction for corporate profits

In the public sector, services are simultaneously produced and consumed to solve shared problems, challenges, or tasks through a constructive exchange of different kinds of knowledge, resources, competences, and ideas (Torfing et al., 2019)

Co-production

Co-production refers to the interactive process through which providers and users apply different resources and capabilities in delivery, and produce public value in terms of visions, plans, strategies, frameworks, through a continuous improvement of outputs or innovative step-changes that transform the understanding of the problem (Alford et al., 2016).

Co-production implies the presence of two types of **participants**: state actors (the so-called 'regular producers'), and lay actors (Nabatchi et al., 2017)

Co-production requires a commitment to **frame reflection** to being open to questioning the understanding of problems beyond the rational epistemology which sees problems within a 'one-size-fits-all' strategy (Paquet 2009)

However...

Inherited **structures** can act as constraints on available or viable options (Peters and Painter, 2010), and existing **norms** can work against efforts at reform (Brown and Head, 2017)

Practices often:

- Represent an 'add-on' and fail to recognize that they are an **unavoidable** part of the service system

- Fall down at the first stage, since context mapping focuses on needs, rather than on needs and **capabilities**

- Are critiqued as framed into a **neoliberal** framework as service improvements are made while wider structural issues are not be challenged (Farr, 2018)

Fifth Part

Participation in the uncertain time of pandemic

What has the pandemic brought in the field of participation?

The outbreak of the covid-19 pandemic is the perfect storm that corroborates the magnitude of **upcoming challenges** for the future of democracy, cities, and citizen participation

The impacts of the covid-19 pandemic in **cities**, where more than half of the world population lives, offers a unique cross section to understand whether and to what extent participatory practices have been pushed forward

Evidence from European cities shows emerging trends of short-term local **participatory practices** focussed on the provision of practical support in different policy domains through online and on-the-field channels

Insights from international sources

Timeframe: most practices adopt a short-term timeframe for immediate responses aimed at curbing contagion, scaling medical treatments and care, and providing safety nets to the most vulnerable

Sponsor: most practices are either promoted or led by public authorities and only few reported practices are organised by the third sector and the civil society

Scope: most practices regard the provision of practical support in favour of specific social groups and economic sectors via information and general guidance; ad-hoc media platforms; public campaigns; formulation of recommendations

Theme: most practices promote solidarity actions; health and care solutions; local food products; culture and sport; urban mobility and tourism

Channel: equal distribution of on-the-field (either public or crowdsourced provision of goods and services, neighbourhood volunteering, etc.) and online tools (e.g. digital platforms, apps, hotlines, etc.)

Sixth Part

Examples

Participatory Budgets

- A picture of PBs in the country:
 - One of the highest rates of **local PBs** worldwide: 1686 PBs promoted by local authorities, schools and other institutions, and 124 PBs implemented by city and parish councils only were reported in the 2019 International Atlas.
 - The first country to hold **national PBs** completely managed by the government since 2017.
 - The autonomous governments of Azores and Madeira also implemented **PBs at the regional scale** in 2018 and 2019.
- The expansion was supported by the **national network of participatory authorities** gathering city and parish councils actively involved in the promotion of participatory processes. This network recently issued a *vade mecum* to improve the quality of PBs, which enumerates 13 guiding principles.

BipZip

Socioeconomic, infrastructural, and environmental indexes at the back of the “priority areas” identified in 2010

A total average of 67 priority areas included in the urban Master Plan of the city

The areas are classified into four typologies:

- Municipal (social housing): 29 areas
- Historical: 13 areas
- Illegal origin (AUGI): 7 areas
- Other/Mix: 18 areas

Local partnerships

The Programme “Bairros de Intervenção Prioritária / Zonas de Intervenção Prioritária” is promoted by the Local Housing and Development Department of the Municipality of Lisbon

The Programme annually allocates around two million euro budget by funding local partnerships consisting of NGOs, Parish governments, and civil society (between €5000 and €50,000 each)

Local partnerships implement urban regeneration-oriented projects in the priority areas

ROCK - Regeneration and Optimization of Cultural heritage in creative and Knowledge cities

The H2020 project ROCK (2017-2020) aimed at promoting cultural heritage-led urban regeneration

10 European cities: 7 role models (Athens, Cluj-Napoca, Eindhoven, Liverpool, Lyon, Turin and Vilnius) and 3 replicator cities (Bologna, Lisbon and Skopje)

In Lisbon, Cultural Heritage-led Regeneration was promoted in a deprived area of Marvila/Beato

Marvila/Beato

Despite geographically central, a socially peripheral area of the city:

Low job occupation and educational rates

Underdeveloped public transportation system, and two railways crossing the area

Unseen cultural heritage (from XVIII century palaces to XIX industries)

Flagship pilots

Pilots:

Pop-up store “Loja ComVida” (“Store with Life/Store Invites”): reuse of abandoned stores through cultural and community-based activities

Garden for All “Jardim para Todos”: Urban farm and a community kitchen towards greener solutions

Interpretive centre: participatory collection of stories and memories

Martim Moniz: history in short

Mid-1950s the space for the square is created (demolition of the parts of the built environment)

1960s: the new **Hotel Mundial** is built and **Metro** stations are inaugurated

1980s: two **Shopping Centres** open on both sides of the square

In 2011 the private company NCS gets the right over the Square until 2022, and launches the **Fusion Market** with 10 small stands

In the end of 2017 the joint venture Moonbrigade (including NCS) proposes the new **Martim Moniz Market** to the city council (until 2032)

The public Forum “Cidadania Lx” launches a **public petition** against the plan; the Movement “Morar em Lisboa” organizes a **public debate** on the future of the Square; and the NGO “Renovar a Mouraria” contends the creation of a green space in November and December

In February, a big **protest** is organised in the Square claiming for the creation of a new garden

Citizens' Council

Quais são os setores responsáveis pela maior consenso de energia na cidade de Lisboa?

CITIZEN PARTICIPATION AND DELIBERATION
SEMINAR SERIES #1: INPUTS FOR THE NEW LISBON CITIZENS' COUNCIL

- 9:30 - 10:00 Opening session
Roberto Falanga (ICS LISBOA)
- 10 - 10:30 Deliberative Democracy: a conceptual framework
Alain Chazotte (University of Geneva)
- 10:30 - 11:00 Deliberative democracy in Spain
Esther González (Universitat de Màlaga)
- 11 - 11:30 Deliberative democracy in Portugal
Marcial Azeiteiro (Fórum em Ciências Políticas)
- 11:30 - 12:00 Lisbon Citizens' Council
Isabel Albuquerque (Lisbon City Council)
- 12:00-12:30 Q&A
- 12:30 Closing session
Roberto Falanga

11 APRIL 2022
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CITIZEN PARTICIPATION AND DELIBERATION
SEMINAR SERIES #2: CLIMATE CHANGE AND THE LISBON CITIZENS' COUNCIL

- 9 - 10 - 10:30: Opening session
Roberto Falanga (ICS LISBOA)
- 10:30 - 11:00 Climate assemblies: learning from best practices
Giuseppe Sestini (INCA - Knowledge Network on Climate Adaptation)
- 11 - 11:30: Citizen assembly as participatory environmental governance
Frank Fischer (Kätechet Daniel Thoen-Institute, Karlsruhe University Berlin) and **Pyeonggi Jeon** (Seoul National University of Education)
- 11:30 - 12:00 Climate change and citizen participation in Portugal
Lúcia Schmidt (ICS LISBOA)
- 12:00-12:30 Q&A
- 12:30 Closing session
Roberto Falanga

16 JULY 2022
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CITIZEN PARTICIPATION AND DELIBERATION
SEMINAR SERIES #3: EVALUATION AND THE LISBON CITIZENS' COUNCIL

- 9:30 - 10:00 Opening session
Roberto Falanga (ICS LISBOA)
- 10 - 10:30 Evaluating citizen engagement in policymaking: the contribution of the working group
Stephen Osoff (Theodore Roosevelt University, Chicago, USA)
- 10:30 - 11:00 Evaluating citizen engagement in policymaking: the contribution of the working group
Roberto Falanga (ICS LISBOA), **Esther González** (Universitat de Màlaga) and **Luís Albuquerque** (Lisbon City Council)
- 11 - 11:30 Evaluating citizen assemblies: why and how?
Andreas Krouwel (University of Amsterdam)
- 11:30 - 12:00 Evaluating the role of citizens in policymaking: what differences are there?
Paula Almeida (ICS LISBOA), **Christophe Depraetere** (University of Applied Sciences - University of Applied Sciences - University of Applied Sciences - University of Applied Sciences)
- 12:00-12:30 Q&A
- 12:30 Closing session
Roberto Falanga

28 OCTOBER 2022
AUDITORIUM SEDAS NUNES | ICS LISBOA

3.3 Citizen engagement in renewable energies and future studies, 29th March 2023

The third session of the training programme comprised two presentations, the first by Ana Delicado (ICS ULisboa) and the second by Giuseppe Macca (ethics4growth).

The first presentation had a mainly introductory aim regarding citizen participation in renewable energy. It addressed participation in Environmental Impact Assessment public consultations and the limits to participation current legislation imposes in Portugal and Spain and the new opportunities for participation that energy communities offer. It also presented the Action Catalogue compiled by the EU project Engage 2020 and highlighted the importance of using methodologies when discussing renewable energy siting.

The second presentation introduced future studies (Miller 2018) and their application to citizen engagement. Macca exhorted participants to fill in a brief survey (Figures 3.3.1 and 3.3.2) and provided examples of how future labs are used to discuss with citizens topics such as participatory planning, development strategies, student counselling, and designing places and spaces.

Figure 3.3.1 Brief online survey about perceptions of the future

Figure 3.3.2 Survey results on perceptions of the future

3.3.1 Presentations slides: part I

PLANNING AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES H2020-MSCA-RISE 2017 – 778039 PEARLS

Training on methodologies for public engagement

WPS Social Innovation

27-29 March 2023

Citizen engagement and renewable energies

Ana Delicado and Giuseppe Macca

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778039

Public participation in renewable energy

Environmental Impact Assessment

Public participation in renewable energy

• EIA public consultations are usually:

- Done online
- Poorly publicised, short deadlines
- Hard to understand technical information
- Require written comments
- Technical arguments are valued above all other kinds of arguments
- Projects approved despite unfavourable comments

Public participation in renewable energy

GOVERNO Governo reduz necessidade de avaliação de impacto ambiental na produção de renováveis

O objetivo é acelerar a transição energética, tendo em conta a crise energética gerada pelo aumento dos preços dos combustíveis fósseis

El Gobierno desmantela la Evaluación de Impacto Ambiental para dar luz verde exprés a decenas de megaparques eólicos y solares

Asociación Luna Verde León @LeonAsociacion

El MITECO está aprovechando la desconexión informativa de estas fechas navideñas para publicar en el BOE numerosas D.I.A. favorables de parques eólicos invasivos por su elevado impacto ambiental, paisajístico, socioeconómico o patrimonial en Teruel, Burgos o Cantabria.

5:54 pm · 27 Dec 2022 · 2993 Views

Lunes, 29 de enero de 2023

Asociación Luna Verde León @LeonAsociacion · 27 Dec 2022
El MITECO está admitiendo proyectos con miles de alegaciones en contra, incluso de las Entidades Locales (administraciones públicas) propietarias de los montes, afectando a Red Natura 2000, especies en peligro de extinción, elementos patrimoniales y paisajísticos...

Public participation in renewable energy

Eólicas no mar. Movimiento de pescadores rechaza "deserto oceánico" nos 320 mil hectareas propostos

Porta-voz de movimiento da pesca diz que setor se sente "traído" por ter sido excluído da proposta que cria cinco áreas de eólicas no mar e rechaza "deserto oceánico" nos 320 mil hectareas envolvidos.

ALIENTE
ALIANZA ENERGÍA Y TERRITORIO

Public participation in renewable energy

- Spain:
 Real Decreto-ley 12/2021
 Environmental, social and economic
 criteria for evaluating project
 proposals
 Rating system that rewards proposals
 that:
- Generate local employment
 - Generate economic impact in the local industrial chain of value
 - Participation of local investors
 - Reinvestment of benefits in the local area

New opportunities for citizen engagement: energy communities

Renewable Energy Community

A legal entity:

- (a) which, in accordance with the applicable national law, is based on open and voluntary participation, is autonomous, and is effectively controlled by shareholders or members that are located in the proximity of the renewable energy projects that are owned and developed by that legal entity;
- (b) the shareholders or members of which are natural persons, SMEs or local authorities, including municipalities;
- (c) the primary purpose of which is to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits¹

Article 2(16) Recast Renewable Energy Directive

Citizen Energy Community

A legal entity that:

- (a) is based on voluntary and open participation and is effectively controlled by members or shareholders that are natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises;
- (b) has for its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits;
- (c) may engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders;

Article 2(11) Recast Internal Electricity Market Directive

Energy communities

Visual methodologies

Krzywoszynska et al. 2018

Visual methodologies

Virtual Landscape Theatre

What is it?

The Virtual Landscape Theatre (VLT) is a mobile curved screen projection facility, in which people can be 'immersed' in computer models of their environment to explore landscapes of the past, present and future. It is used with communities around the country.

Small groups have the opportunity to experience landscapes by moving through the virtual world, add new content, view realistic representations, or augmented with other information such as flood risk, natural heritage designations, wind speed, land ownership, or soil type – and they can provide feedback by means of a voting handset. That way the public can be directly involved in the planning decisions that affect them.

<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/learning/exhibits/vlt>

Wang et al 2015

3.3.2 Presentations slides: part II

GIUSEPPE MACCA
CEO&FOUNDER

PhD in
JURIDICAL
SCIENCES,
MANAGEMENT
AND
ECONOMICS

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI ENNA "KORE"

ethics 4 growth

DOCENTE DI
ETICA E
RESPONSABILITÀ
SOCIALE DI
IMPRESA

UNIVERSIDAD DE
MANIZALES

THE SOCIAL INNOVATION STUDIO FOR
THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE
AND ETHICAL BUSINESS MODELS

RESEARCH

A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE
SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP ITALIAN
ENVIRONMENT WITH A FOCUS ON THE
PERFORMANCE ON THE ITALIAN B-CORPS:

*IS IT A REALLY COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE?
IS IT REALLY AN IMPACT DRIVER?*

Certified

Corporation

UNIVERSIDAD DE
MANIZALES

TEACHING
ETICA Y RESPONSABILIDAD
SOCIAL DE EMPRESA

Future studies applied to community engagement

SURVIO TIME!

<https://www.survio.com/survey/d/Y2P5J6C6A6Q7R6J6Z>

Why do we use future labs

Our studies are aimed at the development of the **future literacy**.

They focus on:

- ❖ **Alphabetization** to the future;
- ❖ Capability of using the future within the **present**;
- ❖ Implement the right to **imagination**;
- ❖ Implement the right to **hope**.

What are the key actions of the e4g future studies

- ❖ They **engage the communities** (youths, local admins, organizations, companies, students, professionals, citizens...) to think over the future of their territory/organization;
- ❖ They elaborate **strategies** to be applied in the present in order for the society to be ready to process future changes;
- ❖ They point out today effective paths to build a really **sustainable future.**

Future studies applied to participatory planning

We carried out **4 future labs** involving **100 participants** during 4 days discussing the topics of **urban mobility, accessibility and quality of life and work.**

Beneficiary: Confindustria Siracusa

When: November - December 2021

Future studies applied to participatory planning

What was the **goal**?

To **identify the strategic guidelines** to plan the social, environmental and economic actions and priorities to finance thanks to the PNRR (Italian name for the next gen EU)

Future studies applied to development strategies

A full morning dedicated to a public future lab in one of the place that most need re-activation: **a city square**.

The workshop engaged 30 citizens that debated and **imagined the city of Lentini (Sicily) in 2050**.

Beneficiary: Badia lost&found (third sector organization)

When: June 2022

Future studies applied to development strategies

What was the **goal**?

Co-planning our city has been designed to trigger the participants into identifying a **common view** for a specific neighbourhood of their city.

The e4g team used the workshop results **to build and deliver a strategy** to the Ngo active in the area that committed the activity.

Future studies applied to student counseling

A workshop involving **35 students** among last year of high school and 1st year of university invited by a local youth association.

Beneficiary: local schools

When: July 2022

Future studies applied to student counseling

What was the **goal**?

The students were asked to imagine who would be the citizen of the future in 2040 and what kind of citizens will they be by then.

The e4g team has delivered to teachers and tutors a vademecum of personalized suggestions for each student to orient and support him/her in career choices.

Future studies applied to designing places and spaces

Four days dedicated to **re-think the future** of a little town in the Etna region starting from a **public place**, the local centre for youth entrepreneurship – a former Mafia establishment.

More than 50 people engaged belonging to **different set of stakeholders** (Mayor, church, university, school, students, local associations, local activists...)

Beneficiary: MIUR – via local NGO

When: November – December 2022

Future studies applied to designing places and spaces

What was the **goal**?

To imagine the future of a place confiscated from the organized crime and to enhance its potential to serve the local communities.

The e4g team **designed a project**, defining timeline, key actions and goals for the local NGO managing the space.

4. Results

The training course achieved most of the expected results. The sessions attained a reasonable balance between theoretical framing, technical advice and practical examples regarding participatory methodologies.

Although we did not perform an evaluation of the sessions, the questions posed during and at the end of each session showed that participants were motivated and interested. The sessions were well attended and participants asked to receive copies of the presentations and the recordings. After the course they were sent a link to an online folder with all these materials.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the number of participants who actually attended the sessions (Table 4.1) was somewhat fairly lower than the number of people who registered for the course. Also, the majority came from academic partners of the consortium, whereas companies and CSO were the intended target audience for training.

Table 4.1 Number of participants by training topic

Date	Topic	Number of participants
27 th March	Toolkit for policy design and implementation	11
28 th March	Citizen engagement methodology	7
29 th March	Citizen engagement in RE and future studies	11

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